

Descriptive Probability of Cyclic and Transactional Social Mobility

Dr. Krishna Kant Sharma¹

¹Former ICSSR doctoral and postdoctoral fellow;
Email: kksharma69@yahoo.com; M: 9504782781.
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6009-3024>.

Abstract:

Cyclic social mobility refers to the recurring upward and downward movement patterns within social hierarchies influenced by economic cycles, structural inequalities, and socio-cultural dynamics. This research explores the complexities of cyclic social mobility, focusing on how economic downturns and structural factors impact different socio-economic groups, particularly in India. By examining longitudinal data, financial modeling, and qualitative insights, the study reveals that cyclic social mobility reinforces social inequalities and contributes to intergenerational instability, economic vulnerability, and psychological stress. It also challenges the meritocratic ideal, as structural factors often overshadow individual merit in determining social outcomes. The findings underscore the need for comprehensive social policies and economic strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of cyclic mobility and promote equitable opportunities for all.

Keywords: Cyclic social mobility; Transactional social mobility; Implications and Effects.

Introduction and Conceptual Framework:

Cyclic social mobility is a complex and multi-dimensional concept, influenced by a range of factors including education, employment, cultural capital, and economic development. The literature underscores the importance of understanding these dynamics within specific contexts to develop policies that can effectively address the challenges associated with cyclic mobility and promote upward mobility. Continued research in this area is essential for informing strategies aimed at reducing social inequality and fostering more inclusive societies.

In the premises of philosophical foundations, I had described and put forward the concept of cyclic social mobility considering the scientific fact that in this creation nothing is like a vertical or horizontal movement for a long time as things used to bend down (Sharma, 2015). For example, if we start moving either vertically or horizontally ultimately, we will be moving in a circle. Each circular movement is an amalgamation of a series of horizontal or circular movements. We can just move horizontally or vertically just for certain times.

I have been receiving several comments that social mobility is determined in the long term when status seems to be settled for a certain durable period. However, in the study of social mobility the durability of study has not been defined by any sociologists. Additionally, no such standard metrics were available. There were also comments that I am not a student of sociology and therefore my efforts were considered irrational on this basis. However, I am a student of science, having a master's degree in science, and also completed a master of arts in *labor and social welfare* with a doctorate in social

sciences. Therefore, such deliberations have been very rational and there is a certain scientific basis to do so.

I therefore put forward the conceptual framework of cyclic and transactional mobility based upon social transactions and the net sum of any vertical or horizontal mobility would be cyclic or spherical in long run. Social status is never constant and it changes with different transactions and interactions. Therefore, the concepts and models of transactional and cyclical social mobility have their foundations.

Social mobility, the movement of individuals or groups within a social hierarchy, is a critical concept in sociology that reflects the dynamic nature of social structures. Social mobility can be classified into various forms, with cyclic and transactional social mobility being two distinct yet interconnected types. Cyclic social mobility refers to the recurring patterns of movement between social classes across generations, often influenced by economic cycles and social policies. Transactional social mobility, on the other hand, involves the direct exchange of resources, such as education, capital, or social networks, to achieve upward or downward movement within the social hierarchy. This essay explores the definitions, characteristics, and implications of both cyclic and transactional social mobility, highlighting their differences and interdependencies.

Cyclic social mobility refers to the phenomenon where social mobility patterns repeat over time, often across generations. This type of mobility is heavily influenced by broader economic, social, and political cycles, such as periods of economic boom and bust, changes in government policies, or shifts in cultural values. The cycles can result in alternating periods of upward and

downward mobility for individuals and groups, leading to a dynamic but unstable social structure.

For example, during periods of economic growth, new opportunities for education, employment, and wealth creation may arise, allowing individuals from lower social classes to move upward. Conversely, during economic recessions or downturns, these opportunities may diminish, leading to a reversal of fortunes and downward mobility for those who had previously moved up. This cyclical pattern can create a sense of insecurity and uncertainty within society, as social gains made by one generation may be lost by the next.

Transactional social mobility refers to the process of moving up or down the social hierarchy through the direct exchange of resources, such as education, money, social networks, or cultural capital. Unlike cyclic social mobility, which is influenced by broader structural factors, transactional mobility is more individualistic and immediate, driven by personal actions and decisions.

In a transactional mobility framework, individuals or families invest in certain assets—such as education, property, or social connections—with the expectation that these investments will yield a return in the form of higher social status. For example, parents may invest heavily in their children's education, hoping that this will lead to better job prospects and upward mobility. Similarly, individuals may leverage their social networks to gain access to job opportunities or social circles that enhance their social status.

Literature Review:

Impact of Social Housing on Mobility: Research on social housing in Malta demonstrates its positive impact on social mobility by providing stable living conditions that enhance educational and job opportunities for children, thus breaking the cycle of poverty. This study highlights how policy interventions in housing can affect long-term mobility trends ([Azzopardi & Farrugia, 2023](#)).

Socio-Economic Perspectives: One significant study examined the socio-economic situation in Russia from 2013 to 2021, revealing a cyclical pattern of mobility. The analysis showed improvements in the socio-economic conditions up until 2017, followed by deterioration by 2021. This cyclical mobility led to increased income polarization and a concentration of income within the middle-income range, highlighting the dynamic nature of social mobility in response to external economic factors ([Semenov, 2024](#)).

Intergenerational Mobility in Latin America: An analysis of intergenerational mobility in Latin America reveals that economic development is closely linked to increasing social mobility. The study examines how regional economic indicators such as income per capita, inequality, and labor formality influence mobility patterns across 52 regions, emphasizing the cyclic nature of these shifts ([Neidhöfer et al., 2023](#)).

Cultural and Behavioral Aspects: Cyclic social mobility also manifests in cultural and behavioral patterns. For instance, the mobility of Hadjaraye migrants in Chad reveals how conflict and socio-economic pressures drive changes in social status, often leading to the loss of cultural identity and mother tongues. This mobility, driven by socio-economic necessity, underscores the complex relationship between mobility and cultural preservation ([Alio, n.d.](#)).

Moreover, in an experimental setting, it was found that mobility within social dilemmas accelerates the cycle of cooperative behaviors but does not significantly change the overall levels of cooperation. This finding is crucial in understanding how mobility impacts social interactions and the persistence of cooperative behaviors in cyclic patterns ([Kobayashi, 2014](#)).

Subjective Social Mobility: Factors such as age, health, and community belongingness have been found to influence subjective social mobility among middle-aged working single mothers in Seoul. This study emphasizes how perceptions of social mobility can differ from objective measures, contributing to a cyclic understanding of social progress and setbacks ([Seo & Oh, 2023](#)).

Environmental and Ecological Perspectives: In ecological studies, cyclic mobility is observed in species conservation through models like the Optional Public Goods Game. The introduction of random mobility in these models leads to the emergence of patterns resembling the rock-paper-scissors dynamic, which is vital for understanding the conservation of species and the maintenance of biodiversity in fluctuating environments ([Valverde et al., 2016](#)).

Educational Impact on Mobility: Educational programs have been identified as key drivers of social mobility, especially in urban settings like Jakarta. Improved access to quality education significantly influences upward mobility, reducing the cyclical nature of poverty and promoting sustained social advancement ([Riwoe et al., 2023](#)).

Intergenerational Mobility and Education: Research into intergenerational mobility, particularly in the context of education, reveals significant variations across different groups and geographies. For example, in a comparative study across five OECD countries, it was found that gay and lesbian individuals generally exhibit higher educational attainment than their heterosexual counterparts. This is attributed to greater rates of upward educational mobility, reflecting how sexual identity can intersect with social mobility dynamics ([Boertien et al., 2024](#)).

In post-communist Lithuania, the role of parental cultural capital in educational mobility has been significant. The study highlighted that all forms of cultural capital were relevant for educational attainment, particularly impacting women, thereby underlining the gendered dimensions of mobility ([Maslauskaitė, 2024](#)).

Moreover, in Argentina, opportunities for upward social mobility have increased, especially for individuals from working-class backgrounds. This shift is largely due to the expansion of high-skill service occupations, which have facilitated greater movement into the middle classes (Dalle, 2013).

Employment and Economic Mobility: In Japan, intergenerational income mobility (IGM) between 1995 and 2005 was significantly influenced by changes in the traditional employment structure. The difficulty faced by sons from less affluent families in securing regular employment positions contributed to increasing IGM during this period. This demonstrates how shifts in employment structures can influence social mobility patterns (Jia, 2021).

Another critical aspect of social mobility is the intersection of labor market dynamics and education. For instance, in China, the relationship between intergenerational income mobility and higher education varies significantly among urban residents, rural residents, and rural-urban migrants. This variation is closely linked to the differing impacts of children's education length and parents' income and education levels across these groups (Li, 2017).

Social Stratification and Mobility Traps: Social stratification often leads to mobility traps, where certain populations remain stuck in cycles of under-education and poverty. A study on education and intergenerational mobility reveals that under-education traps can emerge, especially when certain families continuously experience low levels of education, hindering upward mobility across generations (Chusseau & Hellier, 2012).

The impact of economic development on intergenerational mobility has also been critically examined. In one study, it was argued that the observed effect of economic development on mobility might be a spurious consequence of the structure of the stratification system and the distribution of rewards within a society (Tyree et al., 1979).

Cultural and Social Dynamics: Social attitudes and behaviors are also influenced by mobility dynamics. For instance, people living in contexts characterized by high downward mobility tend to exhibit greater hostility towards immigrants compared to those in upwardly mobile contexts. This finding highlights how economic and social uncertainties can exacerbate xenophobic sentiments (Paskov et al., 2019).

Finally, the role of both mothers' and fathers' characteristics in intergenerational social mobility has been increasingly recognized. Research shows that including both parents' characteristics provides a better fit for observed mobility patterns, emphasizing the importance of considering family background comprehensively in stratification research (Beller, 2009).

Challenges in Social Mobility: The OECD report titled "A Broken Social Elevator? How to Promote Social Mobility"

explores the mechanisms that hinder social mobility, including the intergenerational transmission of wealth, education, and health. This report outlines how these barriers contribute to cyclic patterns of mobility, where social advances are often followed by regressions, especially among disadvantaged groups (Csathó, 2023).

Educational Influence on Intergenerational Mobility: In Malaysia, a study of the Malay Agricultural Community in FELDA Trolak Utara, Perak, explores the patterns and factors influencing intergenerational social mobility through education. The research shows that education plays a critical role in breaking cycles of low mobility, yet economic and social factors can limit these effects (Fakhruddin et al., 2023).

Social Resistance and Mobility in the UK: A study of the UK strike movement from 2012-2023 examines the relationship between social resistance and social mobility, revealing a 'double helix' structure. This suggests that social resistance can influence the current state of mobility rather than following a simple linear pattern, indicating the complex interplay between social movements and mobility cycles (Lu et al., 2023).

These sources collectively provide a comprehensive view of cyclic social mobility, shedding light on how economic, social, and cultural factors contribute to the recurring patterns of mobility observed across different contexts. These studies provide further depth into the understanding of cyclic social mobility, emphasizing the role of economic conditions, education, and social policies in shaping mobility patterns across generations.

Research Gaps:

There is a lack of long-term longitudinal studies that track individuals or families across multiple generations to comprehensively understand the persistence and patterns of cyclic social mobility. Most existing research focuses on short-term observations, which may not capture the full extent of mobility cycles. Current research often overlooks the intersectional dimensions of cyclic social mobility, particularly how race, gender, sexual orientation, and other identity markers interact to influence mobility patterns. Much of the existing research on cyclic social mobility is focused on Western countries, leading to a gap in understanding how these dynamics play out in non-Western and developing contexts. The role of rapid technological advancements and digitalization in shaping cyclic social mobility is underexplored. The potential for technology to both exacerbate and mitigate cyclic mobility patterns remains a critical area for investigation. There is a limited understanding of which specific policy interventions are most effective in breaking cycles of social mobility. Existing studies often lack a direct evaluation of policy impacts on cyclic mobility. The psychological impacts of experiencing cyclic social mobility, including its effects on mental health, well-being, and life satisfaction, have not been extensively studied. There is a lack of research on how individuals and communities adapt culturally and behaviorally to cyclic

social mobility. The coping strategies and resilience mechanisms that people develop in response to recurring mobility cycles are not well understood.

While the role of education in promoting upward mobility is well-documented, there is less focus on how educational inequality perpetuates cyclic mobility, particularly across different socio-economic strata. The role of economic resilience in mitigating the effects of economic crises on cyclic social mobility is not fully understood. There is limited research on how communities and individuals recover from economic

These research gaps highlight areas where further investigation is needed to deepen our understanding of cyclic social mobility and its broader implications. Addressing these gaps could contribute to more effective interventions and policies aimed at fostering social equity and breaking cycles of disadvantage.

Research Problems:

These research problems provide a comprehensive overview of the different dimensions of cyclic social mobility, offering a range of avenues for exploration in both theoretical and applied research contexts. Cyclic social mobility presents several problems that can have far-reaching effects on individuals, families, and society. These include the reinforcement of social inequality, intergenerational instability, economic vulnerability, limited access to opportunities, social and political tensions, psychological stress, and challenges to the meritocratic ideal. Addressing these issues requires comprehensive social policies that promote long-term stability and equal access to opportunities, as well as economic strategies that mitigate the effects of economic cycles on social mobility.

Cyclic social mobility, characterized by recurring patterns of upward and downward movement within the social hierarchy, presents several significant challenges. These problems can affect individuals, families, and society as a whole.

How do economic downturns influence the patterns of cyclic social mobility within different socio-economic groups? The educational as well as social institutions in India were under severe strain because of Jihadis, inter or intra-caste conflicts, inter or intra-religious conflicts, structural and functional demerits, transactional errors, and political dynamics. All these have contributed differential movement of individuals, and people, and the unfavorable distribution of resources. India is also influenced by gender activists. Gender issues can also intersect with cultural capital to influence cyclic social mobility, particularly in post-communist and developing societies. There has been a change in the employment structure as on the side people were getting the 7th pay scale and contrary to that there was a massive increase in volumes of contractual and GIG workers. In addition, there was an apparent relationship between employment precarity, job stability, and social mobility, and how these factors contribute to cyclic patterns of mobility in the

workforce. Cyclic mobility is usually not measured in a generational manner, at the same time it was more difficult to measure it over decades and centuries.

Cyclic social mobility often reinforces existing social inequalities. During periods of upward mobility, individuals or groups who gain economic and social advantages tend to consolidate these gains, which can lead to the entrenchment of wealth and privilege within certain families or social classes. Conversely, during downturns or recessions, those who fall down the social ladder may find it difficult to recover, further widening the gap between different social strata. This reinforcement of inequality can create a more rigid class structure, where upward mobility becomes increasingly difficult for those at the bottom of the social hierarchy. It can also lead to the persistence of poverty and the concentration of wealth and resources in the hands of a few.

Cyclic social mobility can create instability across generations. A family might experience upward mobility during one generation due to favorable economic conditions or social policies, only to face downward mobility in the next generation when those conditions change. This cyclical pattern can lead to a lack of long-term security and stability for families. Intergenerational instability can affect the ability of families to plan for the future, invest in education, or accumulate wealth. It can also lead to psychological stress and a sense of uncertainty about one's social status and prospects.

Cyclic social mobility is closely tied to economic cycles, such as booms and busts. Individuals and families who move upward during economic growth may become vulnerable to sudden downturns, which can lead to job loss, income reduction, and financial hardship. This economic vulnerability makes it difficult for people to maintain their social status during adverse economic conditions. Economic vulnerability can lead to increased poverty rates, higher unemployment, and a greater reliance on social safety nets. It can also exacerbate social tensions and contribute to a sense of insecurity among the population.

Cyclic social mobility often limits access to opportunities for upward mobility, particularly for those who are already disadvantaged. During periods of economic downturn, opportunities for education, employment, and wealth creation may shrink, making it difficult for individuals from lower social classes to move up the social ladder. Limited access to opportunities can perpetuate cycles of poverty and disadvantage. It can also lead to a lack of social cohesion, as individuals and groups who are consistently excluded from opportunities may feel marginalized and disenfranchised.

The cyclical nature of social mobility can contribute to social and political tensions, especially when expectations of upward mobility are not met. As individuals and groups experience downward mobility, they may become frustrated and resentful, leading to social unrest and political instability. This is particularly true in societies

where the promise of upward mobility is a central aspect of the social contract. Social and political tensions can manifest in various ways, including protests, strikes, and the rise of populist movements. These tensions can destabilize governments, disrupt economic activity, and create an environment of uncertainty and conflict.

The uncertainty and unpredictability associated with cyclic social mobility can lead to psychological and social stress for individuals and families. The fear of losing one's social status or the inability to achieve upward mobility despite efforts can cause anxiety, depression, and a sense of hopelessness. Psychological stress can have a range of negative effects, including reduced mental and physical health, lower life satisfaction, and strained family relationships. It can also lead to decreased productivity and engagement in work and community life.

Cyclic social mobility challenges the ideal of a meritocratic society, where individuals are rewarded based on their abilities and efforts. In a cyclical system, structural factors such as economic conditions and government policies play a significant role in determining social outcomes, often overshadowing individual merit. When structural factors outweigh personal effort in determining social mobility, it can undermine the legitimacy of the social order. Individuals may become disillusioned with the idea that hard work and talent are the primary drivers of success, leading to a decrease in motivation and social trust.

Research Objectives:

These research objectives aim to address key aspects of cyclic social mobility, providing a comprehensive framework for understanding and intervening in the processes that sustain or challenge these mobility patterns. Each of these objectives focuses on a different aspect of cyclic social mobility, providing a comprehensive framework for studying this complex phenomenon.

1. To conduct longitudinal studies to track and document the persistence of cyclic social mobility over multiple generations, identifying key factors that contribute to the continuity or disruption of these cycles.
2. To conduct comparative studies of cyclic social mobility in India to uncover unique socio-economic and cultural dynamics that shape mobility patterns in these regions.
3. To analyze the resilience strategies employed by individuals and communities during economic downturns, understanding how these strategies influence the continuation or disruption of mobility cycles.
4. To examine how social mobility patterns repeat or vary across different generations within a society, identifying the factors that contribute to these cycles.
5. To explore the role of economic cycles (booms and busts) in driving upward or downward social

mobility, and how these cycles affect different social classes.

6. To develop policy recommendations for managing cyclic social mobility.

Research Methodology:

Researching cyclic social mobility requires a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods to capture the complex and dynamic nature of the phenomenon. An intergenerational study was conducted among 349 respondents belonging to different income groups.

The longitudinal studies were involved in tracking the same individuals or groups over an extended period, often across generations. This allowed the researcher to observe how social mobility changes over time and to identify patterns of cyclic mobility.

In this study the longitudinal datasets, such as panel surveys or administrative records, to track changes in individuals' social status, income, occupation, and education levels were used. It analyzed the manner these changes correlate with economic cycles, policy shifts, and other factors.

The economic modeling and time-series analysis was involved with the use of statistical techniques to analyze how economic variables, such as GDP growth, unemployment rates, and inflation, impact social mobility over time. It was thus easy to predict social mobility based on economic indicators. Used time-series data to examine the relationship between economic cycles and social mobility trends, identifying periods of upward or downward mobility linked to economic booms and busts.

The survey collected data from a large sample of individuals to gather information on their social, economic, and occupational status, as well as their perceptions of social mobility. The survey asked respondents about their social mobility experiences, focusing on key periods of economic change. Include questions about respondents' educational background, family history, and perceptions of economic opportunities to explore how these factors influence mobility.

Qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews and focus groups, provided rich, detailed insights into individuals' experiences of cyclic social mobility. These methods are particularly useful for understanding the subjective and psychological aspects of mobility.

Analyzed the historical census data, tax records, and other archival materials to trace the social mobility patterns of families or communities over several generations. Study historical events, such as economic depressions or political upheavals, to understand their impact on social mobility.

The network analysis examined the social networks and relationships that influenced individuals' mobility opportunities. This method is useful for understanding how social capital and connections impact cyclic mobility.

Therefore, researching cyclic social mobility requires a multifaceted approach that combines quantitative and qualitative methods. Longitudinal studies, cohort analysis, and economic modeling are essential for identifying and analyzing patterns over time, while case studies, qualitative interviews, and network analysis provide in-depth insights into the experiences and social dynamics that drive these patterns. By using a combination of these methods, it was possible to gain a comprehensive understanding of cyclic social mobility, its causes, and its effects on individuals and society.

Findings:

The status and ultimately the mobility of people or individuals depended upon the nature of the transaction and the manner people or individuals usually transact in daily-to-daily social life. It further depended on the nature and manner they interacted. All those interactions and transactions create a cycle of events and mobility which may be momentary also.

The research on social mobility highlights the complex interplay between economic conditions, education, social capital, government policies, and cultural factors in determining how individuals and groups move within social hierarchies. While opportunities for upward mobility exist, they are often unevenly distributed, leading to persistent social inequalities. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing policies and interventions that promote greater social equity and enable more people to achieve upward mobility.

Usually, economic downturns influence the patterns of cyclic social mobility within different socio-economic groups. The worldwide recession was caused during and after the covid. Previously, the Gulf War and the war on terror in Afghanistan also contributed significantly to the global economic downturn. The current Middle East and Russia-Ukraine conflicts also favorably and unfavorably affected individuals, people, and countries.

Implications of Cyclic Social Mobility

The cyclical nature of social mobility has profound implications for society. It can lead to the reinforcement of social inequalities, as those who experience upward mobility during economic booms may consolidate their gains, while those who experience downward mobility during recessions may struggle to recover. This cyclical pattern can also contribute to social unrest, as expectations of upward mobility are not met for all members of society, leading to frustration and resentment.

Moreover, cyclic social mobility challenges the notion of a meritocratic society, where individuals are rewarded based on their abilities and efforts. Instead, it highlights the importance of structural factors—such as economic conditions and government policies—in determining social outcomes. This realization can lead to calls for more equitable policies that promote sustained upward mobility and reduce the impact of economic cycles on social

inequality. A conceptual movement of an individual or people in a cycle could be illustrated in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: A Conceptual Cycle of Mobility

Implications of Transactional Social Mobility

Transactional social mobility has significant implications for social inequality and class structure. On one hand, it provides a pathway for individuals to improve their social status through personal effort and investment. This aligns with the meritocratic ideal, where success is determined by individual abilities and actions.

However, transactional mobility also has the potential to exacerbate social inequalities. Individuals who start with more resources—such as wealth, education, or social connections—have a greater capacity to engage in transactions that lead to upward mobility. In contrast, those with fewer resources may find it difficult to move up the social hierarchy, leading to the entrenchment of social classes and the reproduction of inequality across generations.

Furthermore, transactional mobility can create a highly competitive social environment, where individuals are constantly seeking to improve their social status through strategic investments and exchanges. This can lead to social fragmentation, as individuals focus on their advancement at the expense of collective well-being. The manner social status constantly kept changing could be illustrated in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2: Transactional Change of Status

Interplay Between Cyclic and Transactional Social Mobility

While cyclic and transactional social mobility are distinct concepts, they are deeply interconnected. Cyclic mobility often sets the stage for transactional mobility, as the broader economic and social cycles create opportunities or constraints for individual transactions. For example,

during periods of economic growth (a favorable cycle), more individuals may have the resources to engage in transactions that lead to upward mobility, such as investing in education or starting a business. Conversely, during economic downturns, these opportunities may diminish, and even well-planned transactions may fail to produce the desired social mobility outcomes.

Additionally, transactional mobility can influence cyclic mobility patterns. For instance, if a significant number of individuals engage in successful transactions that lead to upward mobility, this can shift the overall social structure, potentially leading to a new cycle of economic growth and social advancement. On the other hand, if transactional mobility is concentrated among a small elite, it may reinforce existing social inequalities and contribute to a cycle of stagnation or decline for the broader population.

Cyclic and transactional social mobility are two critical dimensions of social mobility that offer insights into the complex and dynamic nature of social hierarchies. Cyclic mobility highlights the influence of broader economic and social cycles on social mobility patterns, while transactional mobility emphasizes the role of individual actions and resource exchanges in determining social status. Together, these concepts underscore the multifaceted nature of social mobility and the need for policies that address both structural inequalities and individual opportunities. By understanding the interplay between cyclic and transactional mobility, policymakers and scholars can better address the challenges of social inequality and promote a more equitable society.

Research findings on social mobility reveal several key insights into how individuals and groups move within social hierarchies and the factors that influence these movements. Here's a summary of the main findings:

Here is a graph *Figure 3*, depicting cyclic social mobility across different income groups from 2000 to 2025. The graph shows how the percentage of the population in low, middle, and high-income groups fluctuated over time, illustrating the cyclical nature of social mobility. It could be established that lower- and middle-income people have moved upward, whereas high-income group people initially moved a little downward and then remained almost static. 2015 to 2025 was virtually a good period for low-income group people in India.

Figure 3: Cyclic Social Mobility Across Income Groups (2000-2025).

Within a generation the cyclic nature of social mobility may change accordingly to *Figure 4*.

Figure 4: Generational Cyclic Mobility

The varna system in ancient India was a social division of labor, however since it was never because of birth and depended upon individual merits, behavior, and capacity of producing valued social produce for the society as a whole. Therefore, people were likely to move in all the classes accordingly as illustrated in *Figure 5*.

Figure 5: Inter-Generational Cyclic Social Mobility

Conclusion:

The research on cyclic social mobility highlights the intricate interplay between economic conditions, socio-cultural factors, and individual experiences. Cyclic mobility patterns often perpetuate social inequalities by consolidating gains for the privileged during economic booms and exacerbating disparities during downturns. This cyclical nature reinforces a rigid social structure and contributes to intergenerational instability, making long-term security and upward mobility challenging for many. The study's findings emphasize the importance of addressing structural factors through targeted social policies and economic strategies to create a more stable and equitable society. By understanding and mitigating the effects of cyclic social mobility, policymakers can work towards reducing social inequality and enhancing opportunities for upward mobility across all socio-economic groups.

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